

POLAND

POLAND

SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING CHILDREN TO OBOE PERFORMANCE IN MUSIC AND ART SCHOOLS

Toshtemirova Mukaddashon

Republican specialized music school named after R. Glier

Senior teacher of "Oboe" specialty

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"If literature, art and culture live, the nation and the people, the whole humanity
will live peacefully" - **Shavkat Mirziyoyev**

Introduction:

In our country, in the spiritual life of the population, in addition, on the basis of education and upbringing, the issues of forming the spiritual and moral qualities of the students and developing the patriotic culture in them have risen to the level of the important policy of our state. Including the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. PF-4947¹, Decree No. PF-6000 dated May 26, 2020 "On measures to increase the role and influence of culture and art in the life of society", "Uzbek National Status Number" dated November 17, 2017 PQ-3391, dated August 14, 2018, "On measures for further development of the horse", "Education of young people to be morally, morally and physically perfect, bringing the system of education to a new level in quality" No. PQ-3907 on "development measures", No. 940 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 21, 2019 "On the establishment of boarding schools specialized in the art of status", Resolution No. 536 of September 2, 2020 "On the organization of the activities of the Yunus Rajabi National Institute of Music Art" states that the development of this field is under the control of the State. There was another great innovation in the cultural activities of our country, which is interpreted as the proof of our opinion of the adoption of the Law "On Cultural Activities and Cultural Organizations".

Literature review:

The following literature was used during the research: R. Nigmatov's "Practice of oboe performance in Uzbekistan" (Technical guide. - T.: - 2011), R. Nigmatov's "Damli Cholgular Orchestra". (- T.: -2010), Salikhov B., Matyokubov B. History of performance of wind and percussion instruments

¹"Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Strategy of Actions for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan". Appendix 1: "Strategy of actions on five priority areas of further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021". People's word. February 8, 2017 issue and Internet resource: www.uzk.uz.

in Uzbekistan. -(T.:2007). Jurgenson P. Oboy. -M., "Music", 1973, etc., etc., we got acquainted with textbooks, educational manuals, monographs and methodological treatises.

Main part:

Music (Greek mousiche - the art of the muses) is a type of art that reflects human emotional experiences, thoughts, imagination through the consistency or set of musical sounds (tones, tones)². Its content consists of specific musical and artistic images that represent changing mental states. Music embodies various human moods (for example, elation, joy, pleasure, observation, sadness, danger, etc.). In addition, music vividly reflects the will qualities of a person (perseverance, aspiration, thoughtfulness, restraint, etc.) and his nature (customer).

Today, before thinking about how to interest young students in musical education, let's talk about musical instruments. Musical instruments - musical instruments designed to create musical tones or unique sonorous sounds and certain rhythmic structures; it is used in performing music as a soloist or as a team (various ensemble, orchestra, etc.). The sound of each musical instrument has its own timbre, certain range, pitch and expressive possibilities. The quality of the sound of musical instruments often depends on the shape, general structure, device and raw materials used in its preparation.

In ancient times, musical instruments were made of reed, bamboo, wood, stone, bone, metal, leather, silk, coconut, gourd and other raw materials. The voicing can be changed with the help of additional instruments, performance styles (for example, strumming, flageolet, etc.), some musical embellishments. Its appearance dates back to the first periods of human history, and the development process is related to the development of musical art and performance, as well as the development of musical instrument production techniques. Musical instruments are divided into groups according to the source of sound and the way they produce sound. These are stringed (chordophones), wind instruments (aerophones), leather-covered (membranophones), reeded (hemidiophones), plate and electronic musical instruments - idiophones.

The more the students know about the instrument, the more interesting information about the instrument they want to play or the chosen instrument, the more they understand the lives and successes of people who play the instrument, the more interested they become and the more resistant they are to the difficulties of learning the instrument. Today, in addition to traditional

² Salixov B, Matyakubov B. O'zbekiston damli va zarbli cholg'ular ijrochiligi tarixi. -T.: 2008.

methods, students are taught using modern methods in keeping with the requirements of the times.

In modern methods, students are represented not only by playing the instrument live, but also by showing examples with the help of multimedia. In addition, the musical instrument is being taught with interest by giving modern methods. After that, they are introduced to the musical piece and taught by beats. Accompanying children's musical instruments is the most interesting activity, because children's musical instruments are lively, sounding toys that interest every student. Children's musical instruments primarily develop students' creativity and musical learning abilities through performing elements.

The use of children's musical instruments in music culture lessons gives good results and increases students' desire for lessons, interest, and musical learning. Children's musical instruments used in music lessons are divided into two types: stringed and non-stringed (noisy) instruments.

1. Musical instruments include: metalophone and xelophone.

2. Non-musical instruments include: circles, simple wooden spoons, small rattles, drums, triangles, maracas and rumbas.

Accompaniment to children's musical instruments is carried out in different ways: first, students listen to the melody, clap, and rhythmically accompany - those who have clearly performed rhythmic accompaniment to music, children accompany musical instruments - later, passive children also accompany, in order to strive for correct performance. - children's accompaniment on musical instruments is always performed on different instruments - students can be divided into 2 groups: 1st group claps and instruments, and 2nd group can be done by giving a voice method (boom-baka-baka-baka-bum) .

Rhythmic accompaniment on children's musical instruments, playing according to the rhythmic structures shown in the graph, also increases the creativity of students, activates them, develops performance skills and musical abilities in every way. When using any method, students should be encouraged, and their passion should not be extinguished forever. A teacher who knows which method to use in any situation will get excellent results from the students. Our main goal is to educate individuals who are selfless and intellectually mature and who will serve to improve the future of our country.

Materials:

The oboe was created by French musicians in the first half of the 17th century based on the shalmei instrument. For this, the following changes were made to the structure of the shalmei: at first, a simple reed pipe - instead of a

pipe, two separate pieces of reed were attached to each other, a double-tongue-trost was made, the inside of the pipe body and the holes that were pressed with a finger were slightly narrowed. . These changes improved the color of the upper register sounds and ensured the purity of intonation. Also, the body of the instrument is divided into three parts and is shaped like a tapered cone. As a result, it is much easier to configure. This new instrument has 7 finger-press holes, two of which are joined together, and the bottom holes are provided with double valves. When they are closed, the lower key do sound is formed. The sound range (range) of the oboe was two octaves. By this time, different types of oboe began to appear. These are: alto, tenor oboes, used mainly in military orchestras.

By the second half of the 18th century, oboes with a conical body became popular in Europe. Their body is a little narrower, and the tilcha-trost is made wider than the previous one. This instrument, which is closer to the modern oboe in terms of sound, is considered the beginning of the oboe in the French system. In a number of European countries, the use of the oboe with a wide scale continued, and later these instruments received the name "German oboe". At the beginning of the 19th century, the structure of the oboe was slightly improved. In it, the octave valve appeared, then fa - sharp and lower do valves to facilitate the increase of breath pressure (pereduvaniya) and raise the sound to an octave. French instrument masters Henri Bord and H. Deleuze are considered the founders of the oboe in the French system because they made significant changes to the mechanics of the oboe steps. But the new oboe models are very close to the current models of the oboe, developed by the French master brothers Shari and Frédéric Tribert.

The modern oboe is made of a 590-610 mm long African blackwood or tuk in a conical shape. It consists of three parts: upper, middle and lower. The top of the oboe is mounted on a brass pin (mil-nil), with a double reed reed reed. The oboe has 25 holes, 22-24 of which are provided with tasiklapans. There are types of oboe in the German and French systems, and French oboes are distinguished by the purity of their intonation, dynamic range, and lightness of sound generation. Also, it differs by a slightly narrower mensuration, improved valve devices, sharper sound and nasal tone (more sarcastic). The sound of German oboes is characterized by its density, lively, intense but muffled tone. In modern practice, oboes of the French system are widely used.

The main chromatic scale of the oboe is from the first octave D to the second octave C - sharp, and they are played in successive stages. The second

octave D to the third octave C-sharp is repeated in the appliqué as above using the octave valve. Higher sounds are created using a complex application. Sounds below the first octave re are played using additional valves. The oboe is a non-transposing instrument and is written in the treble clef.

Performance and expressive means:

Together with the performance of wind instruments, the teachers put forward advanced ideas on its pedagogy and based the Russian school of wind instruments on the following principles:

- To use the technical skill achieved in the sound of the instrument to reveal the artistic content of the music;
- High artistic expressive performance of the instrument, "singing the instrument";
- Benazir artistic performance, i.e. harmony with the composer's thoughts, not deviating from the set goal;
- Simplicity in appearance on stage, not following different styles and directions.

These principles will serve as the main basis for making disciples in the future. Elementary theoretical and practical lessons acquired by students in grades 1-2-3 will help them master the instrument of their choice in a very short period of time. In this regard, taking into account the musical knowledge acquired before the age of 10, some methodological tasks arise:

- ❖ Getting to know the oboe instrument, its structure and care;
- ❖ Adaptation of lips, hands, fingers and body to the instrument;
- ❖ Teaching about articulation, strokes and breathing;
- ❖ Increasing the level of artistic performance of sound;
- ❖ Introduction to the unique application of the instrument;
- ❖ Ensuring the totality of fingers;
- ❖ Mastering the wide range of the oboe.

At present, in the course of study, many musical schools use the oboe instrument of the modern French system. In order to gain knowledge, in a new style, they start learning wind instruments from the age of 5-7 (transient instrument). This method was included in the program of BMM in 1972 by I. Pushechnikov.

Summary:

In conclusion, in the thesis, we got theoretical information about the history of the oboe instrument, its development stage, and performance music. In addition, both theoretical and practical concepts were given about the traditional and

POLAND

POLAND

modern methods used in learning instrumental music. Information was also given about the families of wind instruments and the technique of playing these instruments. The information given in this chapter can be used as theoretical information by oboe specialists, students of music and art schools, and specialized art schools.

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